

Madani: Jurnal Ilmiah Multidisiplin

Volume 2, Nomor 10, 2024, P. 511-520

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E-ISSN: [2986-6340](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14089134)

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14089134>

Design and Implementation of Smart Highway Streetlights for Sustainable Urban Infrastructure

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Abstract

In order to improve energy efficiency and safety, the project "Design and Implementation of Smart Highway Streetlights for Sustainable Urban Infrastructure" makes use of motion sensor Passive Infrared (PIR), monitoring system DHT22, MQ-4, and LDR sensors. In order to save energy, the PIR sensor only turns on the streetlights when it detects the presence of cars and pedestrians. While the MQ-4 sensor detects gas levels to guarantee air quality standards, the DHT22 sensor keeps an eye on the environment, providing information on temperature and humidity. By adjusting the streetlights' brightness in response to ambient light levels, the LDR sensor maximizes visibility while consuming less energy. These sensors can be integrated into a centralized monitoring system to enable remote management and real-time data collection, guaranteeing effective operation and maintenance. In addition to reducing energy consumption and operating expenses, this smart streetlight system makes cities safer and more environmentally friendly. The study's findings suggest that there is a great deal of room to improve environmental monitoring and lower energy use in urban infrastructure projects.

Keywords: *Environmental monitoring, intelligent streetlights on highways, sustainable urban infrastructure, and IoT platforms*

Article Info

Received date: 22 Oktober 2024

Revised date: 29 Oktober 2024

Accepted date: 12 November 2024

INTRODUCTION

A significant demographic change has occurred in recent years, with the majority of the world's population now living in cities, representing a singular point in human history. A significant 66% of the world's population is expected to live in urban areas by the year 2050. Urban areas are an important hub for environmental concerns, particularly when it comes to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and this must be acknowledged. According to reports, urban conglomerates are responsible for about 80% of total greenhouse gas emissions. Within this range, urban transportation is responsible for a significant portion of greenhouse gas emissions (25 percent), followed by the built environment in cities (32%), and municipal solid waste (5%). Interestingly, a significant amount of the world's energy consumption—roughly 20%—is influenced by urban transportation, with the urban built environment accounting for an additional 25%. [1]

The threat of climate change, which has had a negative impact on the environment, the economy, and the standard of living for city dwellers, adds to this confluence of factors. Concerns about the creation and maintenance of sustainable urban infrastructure (SUI), including the negative effects on urban water management, the urban heat island phenomenon, pavement production, and construction practices, are made worse by these difficulties [2].

As the name implies, smart cities refer to the prudent management of urban areas by employing a wide range of electronic technologies, sensors, and sophisticated communication systems. Here is where the Internet of Things (IoT) comes into play, allowing for the creation of a strong connection between the networks, sensors, and devices that are essential to setting up a smart city. Unique Identifiers (UIDs) facilitate the smooth transfer of data across the necessary network in any Internet of Things system. [3].

Making use of IoT technologies makes it easier to produce new insights and transform

massive data streams into useful information in real time. Human involvement in system monitoring and control is greatly reduced when IoT is integrated into smart cities. [4].

Internet of Things

One of the most prominent and promising uses of the Internet of Things (IoT) is the idea of a "smart city," which is continuously acknowledged. With the creation and implementation of various middleware platforms in recent years, the Smart City paradigm has taken on a significant role in both the academic and industrial spheres. Urban centers must become smarter, leaner, and more interconnected in order to stay relevant. The quick development of urban areas into the biggest cities in the world is largely due to IoT [5]. As a result, human-to-human or human-to-computer interactions are no longer necessary for system control and monitoring.

Infrastructure built

An infrastructure based on information and communication technologies that aims to improve quality of life while reducing expenses is called a "smart city." Smart grids, intelligent road systems, efficient lighting, public transportation, safety precautions, environmental monitoring, parking management, and waste control are just a few of the many fields in which smart city applications are used. The attempt to make a city "smart" has become a calculated reaction to the problems caused by the rapid urbanization and population growth of cities. [6].

Smart City framework

The implementation of smart transportation systems, parks, homes, healthcare facilities, and other infrastructure improves many aspects of citizens' lives under the Smart City framework. For the benefit of the populace, strict data privacy regulations are maintained and the Smart City architecture's components are planned as a vast network. [7].

Additionally, smart streetlights are the foundation for the transformation of cities into smart ones, transforming street lighting and promoting energy efficiency. With countless opportunities for technological advancements and integration, they set the foundation for a more sustainable and interconnected future for urban environments. An essential component of creating a Smart City is automated streetlights. [8].

The Internet of Things (IoT) is being integrated into many different areas, and because of their many uses, smart streetlights may be the key to the Smart City idea. These well-thought-out streetlights improve public safety and well-being in addition to reducing the city's electricity usage. This study focuses on how installing smart streetlights powered by information and communication technologies (ICT) like the Internet of Things (IoT) can improve energy efficiency in smart cities. [9].

Streetlights present financial difficulties and are a significant drain on electrical resources. With an annual electricity consumption of 43.9 billion kWh, they are a major contributor to urban energy consumption, making up almost 30% of a nation's total energy consumption. Notably, streetlights are frequently seen illuminating streets all night long, wasting a substantial amount of energy. Furthermore, compared to major city thoroughfares that occasionally remain empty for prolonged periods of time, their power consumption is still relatively high during the day, even on streets with intermittent occupancy. [10]

RELATED WORKS

Public lighting fixtures that integrate cameras, light-sensing photocells, and other sensors to provide real-time monitoring capabilities are known as smart street lights. It is acknowledged as an important step in the creation of smart cities and is also known as intelligent street lighting or adaptive lighting. With the help of sensors, internet of things devices, and/or outdoor lamp controllers, smart street lights can automatically adjust light levels in response to a variety of variables, including traffic, weather, human presence, and the times of sunset and sunrise. Additionally, these lights record and send data to a central management system almost instantly, giving complete control over every luminaire and information on the condition of public lighting. [11]

In order to enable dynamic lighting and dimming based on movement detection, environmental and weather monitoring, and other features, smart street lights usually use a combination of cameras and sensors. By managing luminaires in groups, smart street lighting systems optimize operating costs and lower energy consumption. In order to create a city-scale network that supports a variety of sensors and applications, smart street lighting is an essential part of the development of smart cities..[12]

In both urban and rural locations, streetlights are essential components of public infrastructure that fulfill the vital function of enhancing nighttime visibility and enhancing societal convenience. The efficiency and functionality of a smart street lighting system are improved by integrating it with IoT sensors and software interaction. Given the requirement to keep streetlights on all night, it is critical to look into ways to cut energy use in order to help create a society that is more environmentally sustainable. [13].

Intelligent street lighting systems could improve people's safety and quality of life. However, their implementation presents two difficulties: they are a large electricity user and put a financial burden on local governments. Municipal governments frequently follow a static or traditional paradigm when it comes to lighting public areas, which leads to inefficiencies because dynamic environmental factors like traffic patterns and light levels are ignored. [14].

METHOD

The System Development Life Cycle (SLDC) will determine the task for this project while maintaining the goals. In addition, SLDC has a detailed description of each level, divided and managed into parts. The stage of creation continues in strict order if there are no simultaneous or numerical steps. Data collection is the process of finding and collecting data required in the process of making the final project. Furthermore, the data is analyzed to determine what will be applied to the final project so that this final project has its own advantages from the street lighting monitoring control that has been made. street lighting monitoring control that has been made.

Design of Study

Using the design of experiments (DOE), experiments are planned, carried out, analyzed, and interpreted in a methodical way. Factors must be carefully selected and modified to produce findings that are reliable and significant. The primary goal of DOE is to gather data in an efficient and methodical manner to gain insight into the relationships between variables and the influence of different factors on the experiment's outcomes.

Project Requirement

To adjust their brightness and dimness in response to vehicle motion, smart street lights need a variety of sensors, microcontrollers, and actuators. The project's sensors, which include motion sensors for object detection, temperature and humidity sensors, and air quality sensors, assist in producing input data and sending it to the microcontroller (Arduino Mega). Additionally, the microcontroller will process the data and send it to the actuators so that the streetlights can continue to function. When the user is able to monitor and control the environment, the microcontroller also transmits the data to a cloud server via a wireless (Wi-Fi) fidelity module, which can be accessed on the user's SHD.

Flowchart

The logic for an automated lighting control system that connects to an Internet of Things (IoT) platform and uses a Wi-Fi module, a temperature sensor, and a Light Dependent Resistor (LDR) to regulate light bulbs in response to temperature and ambient brightness data is shown in this flowchart. The Wi-Fi module sends data to the IoT platform to start the process. The temperature is then measured by the system and transmitted through the Wi-Fi module. The ambient brightness level is then measured by the LDR. The system constantly checks the ambient brightness and keeps the bulbs off if it's not dark. The system then determines whether it has become bright again if it is dark. The system goes back to checking the brightness level if it is still dark. The system turns off the bulbs if it gets too bright. By ensuring that the bulbs are only turned on when required, this continuous loop maintains energy efficiency based on ambient light levels.

Fig. 1. Flowchart of the Study.

Block Diagram

The block diagram in Figure 4 shows the steps taken step- by-step to complete the research and testing phase, as well as the improvements that could be made before data were collected for response optimization. The block diagram was designed initially as a guideline to how the research was laid out.

Fig. 2. Block diagram including the hardware and software used.

Circuit Design

The smart streetlights system's circuit design included five distinct systems: an LED, a motion sensor, a gas sensor, a temperature and humidity sensor, and a ldr sensor. According to Figure, the Arduino Mega + wifi module esp8266, temperature sensor, gas sensor, and LDR sensor were used as inputs in the Smart Streetlights project..

The temperature, gas, and air quality sensors in this project serve as signal detectors that are connected to an esp8266. The sensors transmit the data to the esp8266 once they have reached the threshold value. The information is sent to the mobile application in real time.

Fig. 3. Circuit design including the hardware and software used

An intricate configuration utilizing an Arduino Mega and several infrared obstacle avoidance sensors is depicted in this circuit diagram. The central processing unit is the Arduino Mega, which is powered by a USB connection. It is connected to multiple infrared obstacle avoidance sensors, each of which is interfaced with the Arduino Mega via different input pins. Probably in a robotic or automated navigation system, these sensors are used to identify obstacles. The Arduino Mega, which is connected to a breadboard for simpler component management and wiring, processes the signals from the sensors.

The circuit also has a breadboard-connected array of LEDs that are managed by the Arduino Mega. When obstacles are detected, these LEDs can light up to show the sensors' current status. In order to enable real-time processing and response, multiple wires are used to connect the sensors and LEDs to the proper pins on the Arduino Mega.

Each of the IR sensors, which are arranged in a row, can send and receive infrared signals to identify potential obstacles. By making sure that every component is properly interfaced with the Arduino Mega, the breadboard aids in managing the intricate wiring. This configuration, which clearly displays the sensor's readings (through LEDs), is common in robotics projects where obstacle detection and avoidance are essential. The system, which uses an Arduino Mega, several infrared sensors, and LEDs for visual feedback, is an example of an integrated approach to obstacle detection and avoidance.

Software Used

The software that were used includes Arduino IDE, Solidwork, Proteus

Hardware Used

Arduino mega 2560, module wifi esp8266, PIR sensor, ldr sensor, DHT22, MQ4.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Manufacturing of the Smart Streetlights

The process of creating smart streetlights is intricate and multidimensional, combining cutting-edge technologies to produce intelligent and energy-efficient lighting solutions for urban settings. A comprehensive requirement analysis is conducted at the beginning of the design and development phase to pinpoint particular requirements, such as data collection, remote management, and energy efficiency. After concept designs are developed, technical, financial, and environmental viability are assessed through feasibility studies. After that, intricate designs are made, incorporating electrical circuitry, mechanical structures, and software for control and communication.

Component manufacturing is the next stage, which entails choosing sturdy materials for housings and poles and premium glass or plastic for lenses and covers. Energy-efficient LED modules, different kinds of sensors, and connectivity modules for wireless communication are among the electronics and sensors that are produced. Electrical and mechanical parts are integrated during the assembly stage. This entails constructing the pole, putting the enclosures together, wiring the circuitry, and incorporating intelligent parts like communication modules and microcontrollers.

Testing and quality control are essential for guaranteeing performance and dependability. LED performance, sensor accuracy, and connectivity are tested for each component. Functional checks, environmental simulations, and software testing for errors and performance problems are all included in system-level testing. The streetlights are prepared for deployment and installation after passing these tests. Assessing the current infrastructure, establishing foundations, and setting up subterranean cabling are all part of site preparation. After that, the streetlights are installed, wired into the electrical grid, and configured for best results. To guarantee accurate operation, calibration is carried out under real-world circumstances.

Tool and Component Preparation Phase

The Arduino Mega, LDR sensor, LED, jumper cable, 10k Ohm resistor, breadboard, dht22, mq4, and infrared sensor are the tools and parts being used at this point.

Prototype tool making steps

Automatic street lighting using Arduino Mega-based light sensor:

1. Assemble the parts or tools required to create a prototype for automatic street lighting. These include an Arduino Mega, an esp8266 wifi, a dht22, a mq4, an LDR sensor, ten LEDs, ten IR sensors, enough jumper cables, tenk ohm resistors, a breadboard, and a battery.
2. After that, assemble the parts and reposition the pins and other components in accordance with the prepared design drawings.
3. Prepare the coding and Arduino software that will be utilized in the project.
4. Once the code has been verified, the Arduino software will automatically read it. If there are any errors in the code, the software will automatically notify you and display the location of the problematic script. If it is successful, the message "Done Compiling" will appear.
5. The next step after compilation is to use a USB cable to connect the Arduino to a PC in order to upload the code.
6. The next step is to test test the tool whether it works well or not.

LDR Sensor Testing

LDR The purpose of LDR sensor testing is to determine whether or not the sensor is functioning correctly. To conduct this test, a jumper cable is used to connect the Arduino Mega to the LDR sensor. A 10k resistor is connected to a jumper cable. An LDR sensor testing block diagram is shown below. Light Sensor, or LDR Sensor A flashlight from a cellphone was used for this test. The objective is to determine the effectiveness of the LDR sensor used for light detection.

Fig. 4. Ldr test with light handphone

According to the tests above, the cellphone's light directed at the LDR sensor functions properly; when the LDR sensor detects light, the LED turns off, and so on

Testing sensor infrared

The purpose of testing the infrared sensor is to determine how well it functions when an object moves in front of it. Using a jumper cable, the infrared sensor module is connected to the Arduino Mega for this test. The infrared proximity sensor test block diagram is shown in the figure below.

(a) Fig. 5. Block diagram testing sensor infrared.

Fig. 6. The trend in weight loss of sample and the depth of wear.

From the test results of the infrared sensor, it can be concluded that the infrared proximity sensor works in accordance with its function, namely the sensor is capable of detect objects that move in front of it.

Analisis temperature

During the five hours of data collection, which took place between 15:00 AM and 19:45 PM, the prototype was situated on a residential building's balcony and was tracked via a mobile application. Following data extraction from the mobile application, the data is sorted and monitored by the Blynk app using a DHT22 sensor to obtain significant temperature values up and down, ensuring that the lamp's weather conditions remain ideal.

Fig. 7. Temperature readings versus time

Figure 7 shows that it was not in direct sunlight because the temperature was cool for several hundred minutes. The temperature started to rise at 15 o'clock and got hotter before peaking at almost 18 o'clock. Because of the cloudy weather, the temperature was essentially the same as it was at 16 or 17.

Humidity sensor

The relative humidity in the air, represented as a percentage (%), is the humidity level that the DHT22 sensor measures. With an accuracy of ±2% to ±5%, the DHT22 sensor measures relative

humidity between 0% and 100%. This figure represents the proportion of the air's present water vapor content to its maximum capacity at any given temperature. A reading of 50%, for instance, means that half of the maximum amount of water vapor at that temperature is present in the air. Usually, the sensor data is displayed as an integer or decimal representing the relative humidity percentage.. In contrast to the expected trend with 0.5 kg load when placing concentration against time, the results of the subsequent factorial plotting in Figure 12 (b), which focuses on the mean of depth, show a set of anomalies with the depth increasing as the concentration increases. This is primarily because of the increase in load. The third section of this figure only shows a change in the mean of the depth trend when load is changed. The case is repeated when the primary and secondary parameters were concentrations against time.

Numerous applications, such as HVAC (heating, ventilation, and air conditioning) systems, indoor environmental monitoring, agriculture, and Internet of Things (IoT) applications that need environmental condition data, depend on this humidity measurement. It usually takes a microcontroller like an Arduino or Raspberry Pi to read and use the humidity values from the DHT22 sensor. Depending on the needs of the application, this microcontroller reads sensor data and either displays or uses it. The DHT22 sensor is therefore a reliable and efficient instrument for determining air humidity levels in a range of conditions. Using the Minitab optimization software, the aforementioned results can be plotted into a 3D graphical representation to provide a clearer visual understanding of the effects and results of the tribological testing, with the main factors being width, depth.

Fig. 8. humidity readings versus time

The mobile application was used to track the data collection process, which lasted five hours, from 10:00 AM to 3:30 PM. Following data extraction from the mobile application, the data is sorted and monitored by the Blynk app using a DHT22 sensor to obtain significant temperature values up and down, ensuring that the lamp's weather conditions remain ideal.

Gas emission

The MQ-4 sensor's gas degree shows the amount of a particular gas, mostly methane (CH₄), in the air, expressed in parts per million (ppm). For instance, 1000 ppm indicates 1000 methane gas molecules per million air molecules. This value indicates the number of gas molecules per million air molecules. Depending on how it is calibrated and how it is used, the MQ-4 sensor can detect methane concentrations anywhere from a few hundred to several thousand parts per million. Usually, a microcontroller (like an Arduino) reads the analog voltage value that this sensor generates and converts it to parts per million (ppm) values.

The MQ-4 sensor needs to be calibrated with standard gas in order to produce accurate readings, and environmental variables like humidity and temperature have an impact on this accuracy. Numerous industrial applications requiring methane gas monitoring, home safety systems, and gas leak detection all make extensive use of the MQ-4 sensor. A microcontroller is needed to read the voltage output of this sensor and translate it into gas concentration values in parts per million. The microcontroller must be programmed to interpret sensor data and display or use it in accordance with the needs of the application.^{12]}

Fig. 8. Gas readings versus time

CONCLUSION

The project effectively illustrated how to create and deploy a smart highway streetlight system to enhance environmentally friendly urban infrastructure. With LED streetlights as the output, the system integrated a number of sensors, including ten infrared (IR) sensors, a light-dependent resistor (LDR), a DHT22 temperature and humidity sensor, and a MQ-4 gas sensor, using an Arduino Mega microcontroller and a WiFi ESP8266 module. One of the main results was effective energy management using infrared sensors for motion detection, which allowed streetlights to dynamically change brightness depending on the presence of cars and pedestrians, greatly lowering energy use during periods of low traffic [13]. The MQ-4 and DHT22 Monitoring and controlling environmental conditions was made easier by the real-time temperature and air quality data that sensors' environmental monitoring capabilities provided. Furthermore, the LDR enabled adaptive lighting by allowing streetlights to adjust to ambient light conditions, reducing energy consumption during daylight hours. The WiFi ESP8266 module enabled remote monitoring and control, allowing for real-time adjustments and maintenance notifications, which improved the streetlight system's overall efficiency and responsiveness. Finally, integrating Arduino Mega with various sensors and WiFi connectivity into the smart highway streetlight system proved to be an effective approach to creating a more sustainable and intelligent urban infrastructure, setting a promising precedent for future developments in smart city technologies [14].

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author would like to express their gratitude to the lecturers that assisted in making this project a success, Management & Science University for the facilities and funding,

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